

Comparison of Three Meta Heuristics to Optimize Hybrid Flow Shop Scheduling Problem with Parallel Machines

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Abstract—This study compares three meta heuristics to minimize makespan (Cmax) for Hybrid Flow Shop (HFS) Scheduling Problem with Parallel Machines. This problem is known to be NP-Hard. This study proposes three algorithms among improvement heuristic searches which are: Genetic Algorithm (GA), Simulated Annealing (SA), and Tabu Search (TS). SA and TS are known as deterministic improvement heuristic search. GA is known as stochastic improvement heuristic search. A comprehensive comparison from these three improvement heuristic searches is presented. The results for the experiments conducted show that TS is effective and efficient to solve HFS scheduling problems.

Keywords—Flow Shop, Genetic Algorithm, Simulated Annealing, Tabu Search.

I. INTRODUCTION

SCHEDULING is allocating limited resources (machine, gate, people, etc) to certain task to optimize objective functions [1]. Hybrid or Flexible Flow Shop (HFS) is one kind of scheduling problem. HFS is combination of Parallel machine and Flow shop scheduling [2]-[4]. In addition, it is a generalization of flow shop problem [5]. In HFS, jobs are processed through some stages l . In each stage l , there are two or more identical machine i that can process the job. Fig. 1 shows HFS scheme. The job in each stage will be processed by every machine that idle. The machines have capacity constraint so that only one job machine can process at a time.

Fig. 1 n-stages 2-parallel machine Hybrid Flow Shop

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The notation for this scheduling problem is as follows: HFM | perm | Cmax [2]. The meaning of this notation is as follows: hybrid flow shop scheduling environment with all jobs have identical sequence and minimizing total time to finish all jobs is the objective to be solved. Mathematical formulation for HFS is as follows as given in [6]:

Notation of the HFS model:

J : The set of the job to be scheduled

$|J| = N$: number of jobs

s : Number of stages that all jobs will be processed with the same order.

j : Subscript letter representing job j .

l : Subscript letter representing stage l .

i : Subscript letter representing machine i .

m_l : Number of identical parallel machine in stage l .

B : A very large positive number.

S_{jl} : Starting time of job j in stage l .

$\forall l, l \in s, \forall j, j \in J,$

$$X_{jli} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if job } j \text{ is on machine } i \text{ at stage } l. \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$\forall l, l \in s, \forall j, j \in J, i = 1, \dots, m$

$$Y_{fgli} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if job } f \text{ is before job } g \text{ on machine } i \text{ on stage } l \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$\forall l, l \in s, \forall j, j \in J, i = 1, \dots, m$

p_{lj} : Processing time of job j at stage l .

$\forall l, l \in s, \forall j, j \in J,$

Objective Function:

$$\text{Minimize } Q$$

Subject to:

$$S_{js} + p_{js} \leq Q; \forall j \quad (1)$$

$$S_{jl} + p_{jl} \leq S_{j,l+1}; \forall j, l, l \neq s \quad (2)$$

$$S_{fl} + p_{fl} \leq S_{gl} + B(1 - Y_{fgli}); \quad (3)$$

$$\forall l, i, f, g, f \neq g$$

$$Y_{fgli} + Y_{gfli} \leq 1; \quad (4)$$

$$\forall l, i, f, g, f \neq g$$

$$X_{fli} + X_{gli} \leq 1 + Y_{fgli} + Y_{gfli}; \quad (5)$$

$$\forall l, i, f, g, f \neq g$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{ml} X_{jli} = 1; \forall j, l \quad (6)$$

$$S_{jl} \geq 0; \forall j, l \quad (7)$$

$$X_{jli}, Y_{fgli} \in \{0, 1\} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 2 Classification of search algorithm in scheduling problem

Explanation of the model are as follows: (1) indicates that Q is the completion time of the last job j at the last stage s . (2) indicates that it is impossible for every job j to be processed at stage $l+1$ before every job j is completed at stage l , (3), (4), and (5) are the processing order for jobs f and g on machine i at stage l . These constraints are defined to guarantee that one machine can only process one job at any time, (6) guarantee that one job can only be processed on one machine at any time, (7) provides non-negativity constraint for variable S , (8) restricts that the value of X and Y only have 0 or 1.

To solve HFS problem, we presented three improvement heuristic searches [1], which are Genetic Algorithm (GA), Simulated Annealing (SA), and Tabu Search (TS). We use these improvement heuristic searches to solve identical problem instances to directly compare performance of these three searches algorithm. The problems to be solved consist of small size problem to big size problem that are considerable NP-hard to be analytically solved. By using these searches, the problem can be solved in polynomial time computation. From the experiment result, performances of these three searches are studied.

The structures of this paper are organized as follows. In section II, description of improvement heuristic search, as one kind of heuristic search, will be presented. Detail of improvement heuristic search, which are GA, SA, and TS will be presented in section III, IV, and V respectively. Experiment result will be presented in section VI and closed by conclusion in section VII.

II. IMPROVEMENT HEURISTIC SEARCH

In scheduling problem, there are three classifications of search algorithms, which are exact algorithms, approximation algorithms, and heuristic algorithms as in Fig. 2. Exact algorithm is a complete enumeration search that searches all feasible solution in solution region. This algorithm will give optimum solution. Exact algorithm has limited implementation regarding to computational time for large size problem. Branch and bound is kind of exact algorithm. Approximation algorithm is a search algorithm that uses mathematical formulation to guide the search direction to find good feasible solution. Heuristic algorithm is a search algorithm that uses certain rule to search feasible solution in solution region to find good feasible solution.

Heuristic search consist of two groups, which are construction heuristic and improvement heuristic [7]-[8]. Construction heuristic is heuristic search that start from empty schedule solution set and, in each iteration, one job is added into schedule solution set until all jobs are scheduled. Improvement heuristic search is heuristic search that start from initial complete schedule, generated randomly or with certain dispatching rule and the schedule solution set is improved in each iteration until reach certain stopping criteria. GA, SA, and TS are classified as improvement heuristic search.

The background to use approximation search or heuristic search is significantly less computational time even though this search can only give good solution, optimum if we luck. Approximation and heuristic search is effective for large scale problem size, especially for problems that are NP-hard if it is solved using exact algorithm.

III. GENETIC ALGORITHM

GA was found by John Holland. GA is stochastic heuristic technique that starts from many initial solutions, called population, and using generation to create new population. Population is filled by individual in term of chromosome. Each element in chromosome is called gene. Each gene represents job and the position of gene represents sequence of the job in schedule.

To generate new population, GA makes selection from current population to choose the best individual in current population and uses operators to create the new population on new generation. The operators are: Crossover and Mutation. By crossover operation, GA generates the neighborhood to explore new feasible solution [6], [9]-[12], [14].

A. Selection

This process chooses the best individual with fitness function. The fitness function is:

$$P_i = \frac{f_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n f_j} \quad (9)$$

B. Crossover

Crossover is GA operator to generate new individual to fill the population of the new generation. Parents are randomly chosen from individuals from last generation and selected by crossover rate, that is probability that one individual will become parent. There are many methods for crossover operator [13], which are: Position Based Crossover (PBX), Order Based Crossover (OBX), One Point Crossover (1PX), Cycle Crossover Operator (CX), Order Crossover (OX), Linier Order Crossover (LOX), Partially Mapped Crossover (PMX), Two Point Crossover Version 1 (2PX_V1), Two Point Crossover Version 2 (2PX_V2), and Two Point Crossover Version 3 (2PX_V3).

C. Mutation

The objective of mutation operator is to prevent search space fall into local optima. It hopes that by avoiding local optima, it can give near global optima result. Mutation process is an optional process for chromosome. That is why the probability (mutation rate) number is very small. There are two common type of mutations, which are:

1) Inversion

Inversion mutation as in Fig. 3 is method to randomly change the position of gene with other gene in chromosome.

Fig. 3 Mutation Inversion

2) Pairwise Interchange

Pairwise interchange as in Fig. 4 is method to change the position between two adjacent genes in chromosome.

Fig. 4 Mutation Pairwise

Genetic Algorithm Step:

STEP 1: Generate initial population P(0) randomly and set i=0

STEP 2: REPEAT

- a. Evaluate the fitness function of each individual and select the fittest individual from the population that

have:

$$P_i < P_f = \frac{f_f}{\sum_{j=1}^n f_j} \quad (10)$$

- b. Apply crossover according to crossover rate.
- c. Apply mutation according to mutation rate.
- d. produce offspring or child until the population is filled up.

STEP 3: UNTIL Stopping criteria is satisfied.

In Fig. 5, scheme of GA is presented. From the scheme, not every new individual, resulted from crossover operation, will be mutated. Only some new individual will be mutated depend on its mutation rate.

Fig. 5 GA scheme

Maximum 70% populations of next generation are chosen by roulette wheel method using fitness function (9). The rest of the populations will be filled by crossover operation that is done from crossing two random individuals, according to crossover rate, from populations of the last generation. The crossover processes will be iteratively done until individuals in the next generation reach the population size. Subsequently, mutation operation will be done to some individuals in new generation according to its mutation rate.

IV. SIMULATED ANNEALING

SA is one of improvement heuristic search. SA is more deterministic compared to GA. SA starts from one initial solution and, in each iteration, new solution will be generated to improve the solution. SA allows accepting bad solution in certain probability, called probability acceptance test. With

probability acceptance test, it can avoid local optima while searching around the neighborhood. SA uses interchange operator to generate its neighborhood. There are two most common interchange operators, which are SWAP and Pairwise Interchange. In GA, these two operators are used to escape from local optima instead of generating neighborhood.

In the beginning, Final, Current, and Candidate have identical initial solution. Then, in each iteration, current solution is compared with Final solution that has been recorded, if current solution is better than the final solution, then current solution will become candidate solution, if it is not, with some probability, this worst current solution can still be acceptable. The process continues until stopping criteria is reached.

Simulated Annealing Algorithm:

Let:

- Sf = Final Solution found so far.
- Sc = Candidate Solution.
- Sk = Solution on *K*th Iteration.
- F(Sf) = Value of Final Solution.
- F(Sc) = Value of Candidate Solution.
- F(Sk) = Value of *K*th Iteration.
- $P(F(S_k), F(S_c))$ = Probability from moving from Sk schedule to Sc Schedule.

$$e^{-\frac{F(S_k) - F(S_c)}{\beta}}$$

where :

$$\beta = \beta \times \alpha = \text{cooling parameter and } \alpha = [0,1]$$

STEP 1: Set k = 1

- Set β_1 and α
- Set initial solution S1
- Set Sf = S1
- Set F(Sf) = F(S1)

STEP 2: Generate K+1 solution (using SWAP or Pairwise Interchange)

- Evaluate F(Sk)
- IF $F(S_k) < F(S_f)$ which is better THEN
 - Sc = Sk
 - Sf = Sk
 - F(Sf) = F(Sk)
- ELSE
 - Calculate $P(F(S_k), F(S_c))$
 - Generate Random Number U[0,1]
 - IF $U < P(F(S_k), F(S_c))$ THEN
 - Sc = Sk
 - ELSE
 - Sk+1 = Sk

STEP 3: Set k = k+1 and $\beta = \beta \times \alpha$

- IF k = N THEN STOP
- ELSE GOTO STEP 2

V. TABU SEARCH

TS has similar characteristic with SA which is starting from one initial solution and iteratively generate new solution to search through its neighborhood [9]. In TS, acceptance of moving to other solution in neighborhood is not probabilistic like SA, but deterministic. Records of move, called Tabu move, are kept in a list, called Tabu list as in Fig. 6. The function of Tabu list is to remember moves that have been done, so that it will avoid identical move.

Fig. 6 Tabu List

Similar to SA, TS uses interchange operator to generate neighborhood. There are two common operators: SWAP and Pairwise Interchange. In each iteration, TS does more than one neighborhood generation. This is called Inner Step. Examples of three inner steps are shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 Example of inner step

Before generating the neighborhood, TS move will be checked in tabu list. After new solution neighborhoods generated, the best solution on its iteration will be chosen as the parent for the next solutions generation.

Tabu Search Algorithm:

STEP 1: Initialization.

- Set k = 1
- Generate initial solution S0
- Set S1 = S0, then $G(S1) = G(S0)$

STEP 2: Moving.

- Select Sc from neighborhood of Sk
- IF move from Sk to Sc is already in Tabu list THEN
 - Sk+1 = Sk,
 - GOTO STEP 3
- END IF
- IF $G(S_c) < G(S_0)$ THEN
 - S0 = SC
- END IF
- Delete the Tabu move in the bottom of Tabu list
- Add new Tabu Move in the top of Tabu list

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GOTO STEP 3
STEP 3: Next Iteration.
  Set k = k + 1
  IF k = N THEN
    STOP
  ELSE
    GOTO STEP 2
  END IF
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VI. EXPERIMENT RESULT

This experiment uses data from [15] that is originally Tailard's problem set. These benchmark problems consist of 12 problem sets. Each problem sets consist 10 problem instances. On each problem instances, 14 solutions will be presented resulted from 10 GA solutions, 2 SA solutions, and 2 TS solutions. 10's GA solutions are resulted from 10 different crossover operations. Crossover operator is chosen to differentiate the result because crossover operators are the way GA generated new neighborhood or solutions. Crossover operators that are used: PBX, OBX, 1PX, CX, OX, LOX, PMX, 2PX_V1, 2PX_V2, and 2PX_V3. Pairwise interchange is used for GA mutation operation. SWAP and pairwise interchange are neighborhood generation method for SA and TS to get different result. Then, total number of run are 12 Problem sets \times 10 problems instances on each problem set \times 14 different solution approach = 1680 number of runs.

Naming system of the problem set are tai_NumberOfJobs_NumberOfStages. i.e. tai_50_20a is HFS problem with 500 jobs, 20 stages, and subtype problem a. All stages of the problem consist of two identical parallel machines.

Parameters setting for GA are population size = 100, Number of generation = 100, Crossover ratio = 0.9, and Mutation ratio = 0.1. Parameters setting for SA are Cooling parameter = 100, α = 0.8, and number of iterations = 1000. Parameters setting for TS are Tabu List size = 20, Number of inner steps = 5, and number of iteration = 1000. Computer specifications to run all problems are Intel Core 2 Duo 2 GHz, 1GB DDR2 Memory, 80 GB hardisk, and Windows XP SP2 operating system.

Results from run of all problem sets are shown in TABLEIA, IB, and IC. The results are average result from 10 problems in each problem set. The run results consist of 14 solutions of average Cmax and average computation time from each problem set.

In TABLEII, the best solutions of Cmax from each problem set are presented. On each problem set, method that gives the best result is shown as well as result of percent (%) improvement compared with the other methods. TS gives 6 best results, SA gives 3 best results, and GA gives 3 best results. All the best results of TS and SA are resulted from SWAP neighborhood generation. And, the best results from GA are mostly resulted from OX, PMX, and 2PX_V2 crossover. TS gives most of the best result because it uses 5 inner steps to generate neighborhoods in each iteration. It will

make TS can widely explore feasible solution space. It increases the probability to find optimal solution. In GA, crossover rate used is 0.9; it means that 90% probability of gene will become parents to create new population. It makes feasible solution space, explored by GA, become narrow so that it reduces the probability to find optimal solution.

In Fig. 8, comparison of computation time is shown. SA has the minimum computation time and GA has the maximum computation time. In this experiment, TS computation time is between SA and GA computation time. For SA, computation time only depends on problem size and number of iteration. But, for GA and TS, computation time is not merely depending on problem size and number of iteration (in GA, number of generation). GA computation time also depends on population size and TS computation time also depends on number of inner steps. From the graph in Fig. 8, TS algorithm is efficient to solve the problem in computation time and effective to solve HFS problems.

TABLE IA
 AVERAGE CMAX AND COMPUTATIONAL TIME

Problem Set	GA PBX		GA OBX		GA CX		GA OX		GA 1PX	
	Cmax	Time (s)	Cmax	Time (s)						
tai_20_5	744.4	32.2	767.5	34.6	745.2	30.9	746.1	31.3	755.7	31.4
tai_20_10	1046.3	42.6	1069.4	42.7	1040.1	43.6	945.6	44.6	1042.3	41.9
tai_20_20	1656.8	74.5	1682.9	74.8	1659.3	85.8	1656.5	146.9	1660.8	85.4
tai_50_5	1532.4	152.2	1552.4	125.9	1525.8	135.9	1520	134.6	1527.3	137.2
tai_50_10	1918.5	158.7	1953.1	168	1913.1	159	1913.9	161.8	1914.4	175.7
tai_50_20	2515.5	225.6	2647.6	297.8	2606	210.7	2605.8	210.6	2617.6	347.8
tai_100_5	2802.7	490.9	2854.4	493.8	2801.2	456.9	2799.7	651.4	2808.6	574.4
tai_100_10	3324.6	550.2	3360	543	3304.3	544	3312.6	571.7	3309.3	735.7
tai_100_20	4123.8	594.4	4170.7	626.7	4116.4	597.1	4113.2	604.2	4127.6	591.4
tai_200_10	5962.8	1573.1	6042.9	1531.6	5952.3	1619.2	5952.6	1587.9	5971.4	1638.6
tai_200_20	6926.3	1814.5	7001.8	1772.5	6922.4	1823.8	6931.2	1840.1	6922.3	1901.6
tai_500_20	15041	9037.5	15134	9107	14986	9107	15024	9117	15033.5	8917

TABLE IB
 AVERAGE CMAX AND COMPUTATIONAL TIME CONTINUED

Problem Set	GA LOX		GA PMX		GA 2PX V1		GA 2PX V2		GA 2PX V3	
	Cmax	Time (s)	Cmax	Time (s)	Cmax	Time (s)	Cmax	Time (s)	Cmax	Time (s)
tai_20_5	751.3	30.8	748.4	37.1	755.7	36.2	750.2	30.6	750.8	34.4
tai_20_10	1042.5	45.4	1047	43.7	1053.9	40.6	1042.1	49.1	1048.3	44.9
tai_20_20	1663.2	173	1662.1	74.6	1684.7	85.5	1663.3	143.1	1661.5	98.7
tai_50_5	1536.7	135.5	1520.3	135.3	1545.4	313.9	1515.1	205.7	1528.9	132.6
tai_50_10	1923.7	172.2	1919.5	180.3	1919.6	191.7	1905.1	171	1917.8	167.7
tai_50_20	2615.3	222.8	2505.8	217.8	2622.2	225.7	2605.7	230.5	2608	209
tai_100_5	2827.3	434.1	2805.1	458.6	2815.3	525.8	2812.8	524	2800.4	541.1
tai_100_10	3326.8	492.8	3314.2	515.3	3315.6	480.9	3314.9	487.8	3307.8	488.9
tai_100_20	4129.2	605.4	3752.6	597	4125.3	631.2	4121.2	631.2	4120.5	607.2
tai_200_10	5996.6	1565.2	5948.8	1871.4	5973.2	1737.4	5940.1	1722.5	5962.6	1777.3
tai_200_20	6922.3	1801.9	6909.6	1748.4	6948.3	1734.1	6944.6	1762.2	6943.6	1766.4
tai_500_20	15063.5	9017	14995	9147.5	15029	9017.5	14988	9013	14957	9023

TABLE IC
 AVERAGE CMAX AND COMPUTATIONAL TIME CONTINUED

Problem Set	SA Swap		SA Pairwise		TS Swap		TS Pairwise	
	Cmax	Time (s)	Cmax	Time (s)	Cmax	Time (s)	Cmax	Time (s)
tai_20_5	709.7	3.7	784.8	8.7	731.9	16.8	830.6	2.3
tai_20_10	996.1	8.1	1104.3	5	1032.6	16.4	1118.9	2.6
tai_20_20	1650.8	11.8	1702.7	7.5	1654.9	31.8	1775.4	1.5
tai_50_5	1456.9	22.3	1596.1	30.9	1452.2	67.8	1636.2	64.3
tai_50_10	1845.2	20.1	1967.6	20.9	1810.3	76.3	2001.6	50.4
tai_50_20	2508.6	42.7	2714.9	22.9	2527.7	101.2	2737.2	64.5
tai_100_5	2714.3	49.6	2933.1	55.7	2586.6	208.5	2941.5	171.4
tai_100_10	3196	123.9	3367.4	56.5	3138.9	358.2	3439.2	206.3
tai_100_20	4037.2	65.5	4195.9	91.6	3990.8	276.6	4233	237.1
tai_200_10	5759.8	168.4	6104	172.8	5658.1	783.5	6160.8	752.2
tai_200_20	6820.9	212.8	7044.1	243.1	6770.2	870.7	7066.8	854.5
tai_500_20	14679	827	15233	849	14833	3041.5	15268	3049.5

TABLE II
 THE BEST RESULT FROM EACH PROBLEM SET

Problem Set	Method	The Best Cmax	Time(s)	% improvement from GA	% improvement from SA	% Improvement from TS
tai_20_5	SA SWAP	709.7	3.7	4.60%	-	3.03%
tai_20_10	GA OX	945.6	44.6	-	5.06%	8.42%
tai_20_20	SA SWAP	1650.8	11.8	0.34%	-	0.24%
tai_50_5	TS SWAP	1452.2	67.8	4.15%	0.32%	-
tai_50_10	TS SWAP	1810.3	76.3	4.97%	1.89%	-
tai_50_20	GA PMX	2505.8	217.8	-	0.11%	0.87%
tai_100_5	TS SWAP	2585.6	208.5	7.61%	4.70%	-
tai_100_10	TS SWAP	3138.9	358.2	5.21%	1.78%	-
tai_100_20	GA PMX	3752.6	597	-	7.04%	5.96%
tai_200_10	TS SWAP	5658.1	783.5	4.74%	1.76%	-
tai_200_20	TS SWAP	6770.2	870.7	2.01%	0.74%	-
tai_500_20	SA SWAP	14679	827	8.00%	-	1.03%

Fig. 8 Comparison of computation time

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented three improvement heuristic searches, which are GA, SA, and TS, to solve HFS scheduling problems with parallel machines that is known to be NP-hard. The problem consists of two identical parallel machines in each stage. Experiment uses problem from tailard [15] that has problem size ranging from 20 jobs to 500 jobs. Effectiveness and efficiency comparisons of the three improvement heuristic searches are presented. From the experiment result, TS gives effective result and efficient computation time to solve HFS scheduling problems.

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